

EVERYFISH

D5.1 FISHING ACTIVITY DETECTION AND FINGERPRINTING METHODS

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	Lead beneficiary: University of St. Andrews		
	Prepared by: Tania Mendo, Meixuan Liu, Theoni Photopoulou, Jonathan Stoundberg, Gildas Glemarec, Marie Storr-Paulsen, Esmé Maxwell		
Approved by: Rachel Haug Fossbakk, SO			

Abstract

This deliverable describes the methods developed to improve fishing activity detection and produce a clear quantitative “behavioural fingerprint”. A behavioural fingerprint is defined by a collection of features that are measured for each trip, including behaviour (movement, fishing activities) outcomes (catches) and environmental conditions. Trips or vessels whose behaviour falls outside of the expected range that characterises its normal operating region can be flagged for review and enable more efficient targeted inspections for control and monitoring agencies to deter Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated (IUU) fishing activities.

Dissemination level

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CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission services)	
CI	Classified information (as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC)	

Deliverable type

R	Document, report	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC	Web sites, patent fillings, videos, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

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Editor	Tania Mendo
Contributing partners	Technical University of Denmark, SINTEF Ocean, Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries

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EVERYFISH consortium

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The consortium members are:

	<p>SINTEF Ocean (SO) Postboks 4762 Torgard N-7465 Trondheim NORWAY www.sintef.no</p>	<p>Project Coordinator and Manager: Rachel Tiller Rachel.tiller@sintef.no</p>
	<p>Institute of Marine Research (IMR) Postboks 1870 Nordnes 5817 Bergen NORWAY www.hi.no</p>	<p>Helge Sagen Helge.sagen@hi.no</p>
	<p>DTU Aqua (DTU) Danmarks Tekniske Universitet Willemoesvej 2 9850 Hirtshals DENMARK www.dtu.dk</p>	<p>Jordan Feekings jpfe@aqua.dtu.dk</p>
<p>DIRECTORATE OF FISHERIES</p>	<p>Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries (NDF) Postboks 185 Sentrum 5804 Bergen NORWAY www.fiskeridir.no</p>	<p>Ole Høstmark Ole.hostmark@fiskeridir.no</p>
<p>MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE</p>	<p>AZTI-Tecnalia (AZTI) 48395 Sukarrieta SPAIN www.azti.es</p>	<p>Iñaki Quincoces iquincoces@azti.es</p>
	<p>Melbu Systems AS Sminessgata 3, 8445 Melbu NORWAY http://www.melbusystems.no/</p>	<p>Einar Roger Pettersen einar@melbusystems.no</p>
	<p>Çukurova University Fisheries Faculty 01330, Sarıcam, Adana TURKEY http://www.cu.edu.tr/Eng/Default.aspx</p>	<p>Gökhan Gökçe gokhan.gokce@gmail.com</p>
<p>Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food</p>	<p>Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO) Burgemeester Van Gansberghelaan 92 box 1 9829 Merelbeke BELGIUM https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/en</p>	<p>Els Torreële Els.torreële@ilvo.vlaanderen.be</p>
	<p>Wageningen University (WU) P.O. Box 9101 6700 HB Wageningen THE NETHERLANDS www.wur.nl</p>	<p>Gert Kootstra gert.kootstra@wur.nl</p>

	<p>Anchor Lab K/S (AL) Dantes Plads 1 1559 København DENMARK https://www.anchorlab.dk/</p>	<p>Mads Dueholm mads.dueholm@anchorlab.net</p>
	<p>Wageningen Research (WR) P.O. Box 9101 6700 HB Wageningen THE NETHERLANDS www.wur.nl</p>	<p>Angelo Mencarelli angelo.mencarelli@wur.nl</p>
	<p>ASSIST Software SRL (AST) 1 Tipografie Street 720043 Suceava ROMANIA https://assist-software.net/</p>	<p>Catalin Trufin catalin.trufin@assist.ro</p>
	<p>Data Fish Technology Solutions SL (DATAFISH) Bizkaiko Jaurerria Kalea 2 48370 Bermeo (Bizkaia) SPAIN https://datafishts.com/</p>	<p>Nicolás Troncoso ntroncoso@datafishts.com</p>
	<p>University of East Anglia (UEA) Norwich Research Park Norwich Norfolk, NR4 7TJ UNITED KINGDOM https://www.uea.ac.uk/</p>	<p>Michal Mackiewicz M.Mackiewicz@uea.ac.uk</p>
	<p>Cefas Pakefield Road Lowestoft Suffolk NR33 0HT UNITED KINGDOM https://www.cefas.co.uk/</p>	<p>Thomas Catchpole thomas.catchpole@cefas.co.uk</p>
	<p>The University Court of the University of St Andrews (USTAN) College Gate St Andrews KY16 9AJ SCOTLAND www.st-andrews.ac.uk</p>	<p>Mark James maj8@st-andrews.ac.uk</p>

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Executive summary

Rapid advances in vessel tracking and monitoring technologies over the past decade have significantly improved our ability to observe and understand fishing activity at sea. Vessel tracking data, electronic monitoring systems, logbooks and landings now provide detailed information on vessel movements, fishing operations and catch composition. A critical step in harnessing these data effectively is improving the detection of fishing activity and developing a clear quantitative “behavioural fingerprint” for each vessel. This fingerprint is defined by a suite of trip-level features, including behavioural indicators (such as movement and fishing activity), catch outcomes and environmental conditions. Departures from this typical behavioural pattern can indicate potential anomalies.

This report presents methods developed and tested through two case studies: the Danish gillnet fishery and the Norwegian bottom-trawling fleet. In both cases, the approach successfully identifies deviations from expected behavioural patterns and flags them as potential anomalies. These anomaly-detection capabilities can support control and monitoring agencies by helping to identify potential infringements—such as exceedances of regulatory soak-time limits or unusual catch-per-unit-effort values—thereby enhancing compliance monitoring and contributing to more effective and sustainable fisheries management.

1. Introduction

1.1. EVERYFISH HEU motivation and background

The EVERYFISH project is a close collaboration between fisheries research, academic, industry, and governance actors, as well as technology providers across the EU and other European countries. These technological innovations will enable the fisheries sector to optimise automatic data collection and ensure correct reporting of the catch in terms of size, weight, and species. The provision of verifiable catch information and improved evidence of compliance with fisheries regulations will streamline compliance activities for both fisheries and regulators, as well as generating knowledge and data for future conservation, research, and governance activities.

EVERYFISH will build on and exploit the work done in multiple previous projects and further develop key technologies to increase their technology readiness level (TRL). In total, EVERYFISH will develop 10 products and apps for automatic catch recording and reporting, as well as guidelines for implementation and integration of EVERYFISH technologies in commercial fisheries in Europe to optimize resource efficiency, improve automatic data collection, provide evidence of compliance with fishery regulations, and reduce the ecological impact of the sector on the marine environment (Figure 1).

The methods and technologies developed in EVERYFISH will be ready for implementation in commercial fisheries. We assess their TRL in terms of the maturity of the underlying technologies in a fisheries context as several of them, e.g. AI, are already quite mature and used extensively in other sectors but still immature and relatively little used in fisheries management. All the products and apps developed in EVERYFISH are useful as standalone systems to provide automatic catch registration on vessels and by fishers that use them. However, their greatest potential will be realised when the data is standardized and automatically transmitted via a distributed ledger, to be used by stock assessors, fisheries monitoring and management agencies, certification companies, and others.

Figure 1: The conceptual structure of EVERYFISH HEU.

1.2. Role of the deliverable

This report presents the results of work carried out in Subtask 5.1.1 of the EVERYFISH project’s Work Package 5. A set of methods for detecting and describing when, where, and how vessels are performing fishing operations—based on position data from AIS, VMS, or similar tracking systems—has been developed and tested through two case studies: the Danish gillnet fishery and the Norwegian bottom-trawling fleet. Once a clear, consistent quantitative profile of how a vessel usually operates – its “behavioural fingerprint”, we can identify unusual events and flag them as potential anomalies. This work contributes to the development of innovative machine learning solutions to detect potential anomalies in fishing behaviours that will enable more efficient targeted inspections and to develop control strategies to stop IUU and promote sustainable fisheries.

1.3. Structure of this document

This document is organised into five main sections. Following the introduction, Section 2 outlines the background and context of the work, including the underlying motivations and a summary of the tasks completed. Section 3 presents each case study and describes the methods used to infer fishing operations and conduct vessel fingerprinting. Section 4 reports the results for each case study. Finally, Section 5 discusses the key findings and provides overall conclusions.

1.4. Relationship with other deliverables

Table 1 gives an overview of the deliverables that relate to the work presented herein.

D5.6 summarises a literature review that was carried out early in the project. Though the review gave some insight into anomaly detection techniques and their application to fisheries data, the main takeaway was that very little prior work has been done specifically when it comes to data on catch composition.

D5.1 presents work that has been carried out in a parallel to Subtask 5.1.3. Anomaly detection, where synthetic data for training and testing algorithms were generated using the fisheries simulator and trialled with different anomaly detection techniques (see D.1.2).

Table 1: Deliverables that relate to D5.1.

Deliverable no.	Deliverable name	Month due	Partner responsible
5.6	Literature review of machine learning techniques applied to fisheries data	M16	SINTEF Ocean
5.2	Algorithms for detecting anomalies in fishery data	M34	SINTEF Ocean

1.5. Contributors

The following partners have contributed to the work presented in this deliverable:

- University of St Andrews (USTAN): Primary responsibility for carrying out the work and writing this report.
- SINTEF Ocean (SO): Provided input with regards to data used and expert knowledge on Norwegian Case Study.
- Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries (NDF): Provided data and input from the fisheries management perspective, and did some initial clustering-based analysis to detect outliers in catch composition.
- Technical University of Denmark (DTU): Lead on machine learning methods for the Danish Case study.

2. Background and context

Over the last decade, fishing fleets have become richly instrumented with tracking and monitoring technology. Routinely collected vessel tracking data (from Automated Identification Systems- AIS, or Vessel Monitoring Systems-VMS), observer and electronic-monitoring feeds, logbooks and landings now capture where vessels go, how they move and fish, and what they catch (Kroodsma et al. 2018; van Helmond et al. 2020). These data have transformed how activities are monitored at sea. Detecting fishing activity by reliably identifying when and where fishing is happening is the first step towards characterising a vessel or a fleet's typical operating style.

Accurate detection of fishing activity is a prerequisite for recognising departures from the norm and underpins downstream analyses for management, enforcement and scientific evaluation of catch data. Being able to recognise unusual events depends on having a clear and stable, quantitative signature of how a vessel or fleet typically behaves, termed its behavioural "fingerprint". A behavioural fingerprint is defined by a collection of features that are measured for each trip, including behaviour (movement, fishing activities) outcomes (catches) and environmental conditions. By learning the usual pattern across these measurements from a portfolio of past trips, it becomes possible to define a vessel or fleet's normal range of values across the collection of features that are measured and construct trip- or vessel-specific reference distributions. Trips or vessels whose behaviour falls outside of the expected range that characterises its normal operating region can be flagged for review and enable more efficient targeted inspections for control and monitoring agencies to deter Illegal, Unreported and Unregulated (IUU) fishing activities.

The approach taken herein uses two Case Studies to define vessels behavioural fingerprints and flag potential anomalous behaviours: the Danish gillnet fishery and the Norwegian bottom trawling fishery.

2.1. Case studies

2.1.1. Danish gillnet fisheries

Traditionally, Danish gillnetters operating in the Western Baltic Sea target mostly Atlantic cod and European plaice, with seasonal shifts to other valuable commercial species e.g. lumpsucker, Atlantic mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*), or turbot (*Scophthalmus maximus*). A drastic reduction in cod quota, following the recent collapse in cod stocks in the region, led some gillnet fishers to relocate their fishery to areas where cod densities are lower, e.g., on sandy bottoms instead of mussel beds. In this coastal fishery, vessels generally go out on daily trips lasting 3-10 hours depending on the amount of gear to be deployed. When targeting flatfish (and cod), nets are set during the day and left soaking for between 24 and 72 hours. A fisher will sometimes also set a net near shore right outside the harbour while leaving and haul on the way back a few hours later. Targeting lumpsucker or turbot requires fishers to leave their nets soaking for extended periods that can last for a week or more. All of these features together comprise the soak time fingerprint of this fishing fleet.

Recent methods have been developed to infer the fishing activity of small-scale fisheries from high-resolution geospatial data (Mendo et al. 2019; Rufino et al. 2023) and, subsequently, to estimate soak time (Mendo et al. 2023; Sales Henriques et al. 2023). These approaches have been successfully tested in different fisheries, including the Danish gillnet lumpsucker fishery, and have shown promising results when applied to data from Electronic Monitoring (EM) systems, which provide high-frequency positional data (up to every 10 seconds). However, only a limited number of vessels in Denmark are currently equipped with EM, while Automated Identification Systems (AIS) and Vessel Monitoring Systems (VMS) are far more widespread, at least for the largest vessels in this fleet segment. Both AIS and VMS data sources present specific challenges. VMS typically records vessel positions at intervals of up to two hours, which can lead to a severe underestimation of the number of fishing operations (Katara and Silva 2017; Muench et al. 2018). AIS, while offering higher temporal resolution, is constrained by patchy coastal and offshore coverage (James et al. 2018; Shepperson et al. 2018) and by the ability of fishers to intentionally disable transponders (Cappa et al.

2024; Welch et al. 2022). These issues can result in substantial spatiotemporal gaps in tracking data, confounding the reliable estimation of both fishing effort and soak time.

The present study evaluates the feasibility of using AIS and VMS data to estimate soak time in the Danish gillnet fishery, using highly resolved EM data for training and validation. The goal is to generate a soak time fingerprint for this fishery. Leveraging data sources that are widely available across the fleet has the potential to provide valuable insights into fishing effort, while also supporting fisheries management and enforcement. Although we used here as a case study the Danish gillnet fleet seasonally targeting various species (cod, saithe, plaice, turbot, sole, lumpsucker, etc.), it is worth noting that a fleet-wide maximal regulatory soak time is not enforced neither in Denmark nor at the EU level. There are nonetheless exceptions, where such maximal soak time is enforced, e.g., for fishing vessels targeting hake with bottom set gillnet or anglerfish with entangling nets in ICES divisions 3a and 4a (EU Reg. 1241/2019) the maximum allowed soak time is 24 and 72 hours, respectively. In all cases, the ability to estimate soak time from AIS and VMS data could help control agencies identify potential infringements of regulatory soak time limits when such soak time limits are effectively implemented, thereby improving compliance monitoring in small-scale gillnet fisheries.

2.1.2. Norwegian bottom trawling fisheries

After discussions with the Norwegian Directorate (NDF), the demersal trawl whitefish fishery was selected as a Case study. SINTEF Ocean provided advice to restrict the data to the appropriate fishery. The geographic area was restricted to include waters north of 62°N (aligned with Norwegian regulations), east of 11°W, and west of 68°E. The FAO areas included were 27.1.A, 27.1.B, 27.2.A.1, 27.2.A.2, 27.2.B.1, and 27.2.B.2. The fishery definition was further refined by selecting vessels using demersal trawl gear, such as bottom otter trawls, pair trawls, and similar trawl types. Data from 2023 were selected to benefit of more recent, higher-quality NDF data. To ensure the analysis focused on the whitefish fishery, each catch was required to have cod, saithe, or haddock as the main species by weight, though other species could still be present. In practice, the queries also restricted the selection to vessels in length group 5 (28 metres or longer), as smaller vessels were expected to exhibit different underlying statistical patterns that could influence the analysis. The Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries (NDF) makes fisheries data—including ERS, landings, VMS, and vessel information—publicly available on its website for download, and is almost certainly the only fisheries management authority in the world to do so. This removes the primary obstacle for researchers working with fisheries: the most important data is readily available.

The present Case study combines fishing vessel movement behaviour with catch composition and CPUE from the NDF data to create a holistic vessel fingerprint. With a vessel-aware contextual benchmark in place, trips by a given vessel can be compared with its usual operating style. Our goal is to develop an approach for detecting anomalous fishing trips by combining full trajectories, inferred fishing behaviour (e.g., hauls/sets), and catch outcomes for each vessel within a calendar year. We represent every trip made by a vessel within a year with a collection of features - CPUE, catch composition metrics, month, spatial trajectory descriptors, environmental variables (bathymetry, sea floor temperature) - and employ a classification algorithm to identify trips that are different for the vessel's portfolio. Our approach generates simple flags to support analysts reviewing data in real time, and hypothesis generation for research purposes.

3. Methods

3.1. Danish gillnet fisheries

DTU Aqua monitors the bycatch of ETP (Endangered, Threatened, and Protected) species in the Danish commercial gillnets using EM (Electronic Monitoring) on a fleet of voluntary vessels. The bycatch monitoring programme has run continuously since 2010 with 1 to 11 vessels per year (mean = 7.27; sd = 2.58), registering every bycatch event within every fishing operation. The location, date, and time of each set (when the gear is put in the water) and each haul (when the gear is retrieved from the water) is recorded and offers the possibility to estimate with precision the number of gears set/hailed each day, together with important metrics like total gear length and soaking duration (or soak time) of each fishing operation. Practically, the ping rate of the raw EM data (i.e. the duration of the interval between two consecutive points) is 1 second. After extraction, each point in the processed EM dataset carries information on the position (longitude / latitude) of the vessel, the timestamp (date and time formatted as year / month / day, hour : minute : second), the speed of the vessel (in knots), and a binomial variable indicating the vessel activity: fishing (i.e. hauling) or not fishing (i.e. steaming or setting).

In this study, we focused on the period 2018 to 2024, with EM data from 10 vessels. The EM data was supposed to serve as “ground truth”. A census of the fishing activity of these vessels was used, yet there were occasional gaps in the dataset because of e.g. hardware failure. All fishing trips were controlled for potential errors or gaps and the fishing days with faulty data were removed. The final dataset contained 21280 unique hauls from 4777 fishing days.

3.1.1. AIS and VMS data

AIS and VMS data were combined to get maximum coverage, with data that were seen as generally available for the rest of the fleet. The activity from the EM dataset was then overlapped with the AIS/VMS data to get the “true” fishing activity at each point. This was done by assigning the activity from the EM data to the nearest point in-time, of the AIS/VMS data. Most of the nearest points from EM were within seconds of the AIS/VMS points. No Activity was assigned to points, with more than 60 seconds’ difference.

While EM data were available for 10 vessels, only those with consistent longitudinal coverage across both EM and AIS/VMS datasets were selected for analysis. Due to frequent gaps in the reported AIS/VMS data (Figure 2), only four vessels were included in the soak time estimations (ldXTcf, EXIUgY, FrYxWg, xaoePt).

Figure 2 Number of records per day for vessels equipped with EM (orange) and those with AIS/VMS (green). Note that the vessels names have been anonymised.

Data were segmented into trips using harbour polygons, in the same manner as for the EM data. Harbour polygons were obtained from the Danish fisheries agency. These harbour polygons were used to define fishing trips: a trip would start when a vessel would leave the harbour (effectively crossing the polygon border), and the same trip would end when the same vessel would enter the same or another harbour (i.e. the vessel would cross a polygon border again). Any trips with less than 50 observations were dropped, since trips that would last less than 10 minutes were considered highly unlikely (Mendo et al. 2024). Moreover, the data were interpolated to 1-minute intervals when the distance between points did not exceed 500 metres.

VMS is generally pinged every 1 hour for Danish fishing vessels. In the context of looking at gillnet fisheries, a higher resolution is needed to obtain accurate information on fishing effort. To that end, we supplemented VMS with AIS data, which can have varying ping rates, down to one point every 10 seconds. One general issue that we found is that when a vessel is far from the coast, the AIS signal is not received by listening posts onshore. In turn, for vessels fishing farther offshore (e.g. in the North Sea), AIS data was generally missing. Another common issue is that since AIS is primarily a safety tool and not a compliance tool, the fishers can choose to turn the transponder off. At times, the AIS data was missing for some vessels for extended periods or just for parts of a fishing trip.

3.1.2. Predicting fishing operations:

We trained a Random Forest model (Breiman 2001) on the annotated EM data to detect hauling positions from geospatial data input. Our goal was to apply that model onto the AIS/VMS data to predict haul positions. The final model ended up with 30 covariates, most of which were derivatives of speed and distance. Many of the covariates are the same but for different number of points away, such as rolling mean of speeds ± 5 points, or heading change ± 5 points. Other information not relating to the trip itself were used, such as ICES area or depth, which was thought to help distinguish between different métiers that exhibit specific fishing patterns. Each of the covariates was added one by one to the model, starting with speed, and then testing the model performance, with a low number of “trees”.

The hauling vs other activity data is inherently unbalanced data as the proportion of time in a fishing trip corresponding to hauling vs all the other activities is small. To address this imbalance in the data, class weights were forced in the model. Here, we chose to use 20% of the points being “hauls” and 80% being “other activity” (i.e. 20-80 hauling-other). The final model was set up to run with 1000 trees. The model was tested using the leave-one-out (LOO) method (Stone 2018), where the model is trained on the EM data of all but one vessel at a time and then, the resulting model is used to predict on the AIS/VMS data of the left-out vessel. Model accuracy was determined by comparing the ratio of correct predictions (i.e. true positives) between the model results and the ground truth from the EM data for the left-out vessel. Post processing of the model results consisted of filling in patchy predictions or removing spurious predictions. A point was reassigned if the two preceding and following points were opposite of the originally assigned point.

3.1.3. Predicting soak time anomalies

Once hauling events were identified, soak time was estimated following the approach described in (Mendo et al. 2023). In brief, positional data not associated with hauling activity were removed. A spatial buffer (100 metres) was then created around each detected hauling event, and potential setting events from preceding trips were identified. Soak time was calculated by detecting significant spatial intersections between these buffered hauling locations and setting events. The overlap threshold was set to 0.7 (Mendo et al., 2023). Expert knowledge also gave information on minimum and maximum expected soak time for each metier (Level 6, Table 2). Only hauling events >15 minutes were considered and at least 5 minutes between hauling events were needed for a new hauling event. After estimating soak times, vessel-level boxplots were used to identify potential anomalies or outliers, defined here as the values farthest from the rest of the data (1.5 times the interquartile range).

Table 2 Minimum and maximum soak time (hours) for each metier

Metier Level 6	Min soak time (h)	Max soak time (h)
GNS_DEF_110-156_0_0	2	169
GNS_DEF_>=157_0_0	1	169
GNS_DEF_120-219_0_0	1	170
GNS_DEF_100-119_0_0	6	168
GNS_DEF_>=220_0_0	3	170
FPN_CAT_>0_0_0	20	71
GNS_DEF_32-89_0_0	20	75
LHP_DEF_0_0_0	12	25

3.2 Norwegian bottom trawling fisheries

3.2.1 Data sources

For this work, a demersal trawl whitefish fishery operating in 2023 was selected as the focus of analysis. Catch data and vessel-tracking information from electronic reporting systems (ERS) and vessel monitoring systems (VMS), respectively, were obtained from publicly available datasets provided by the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries (NDF). The queries used to subset the data to this specific fishery were supplied by SINTEF. The geographic area of interest was defined using an OR relation, with one specification based on coordinates and the other on FAO area codes. It is important to note that the public NDF dataset includes only Norwegian vessels; therefore, using a broader geographic boundary does not introduce vessels flagged to other states. The coordinate-based bounds were set to waters north of 62°N (consistent with Norwegian regulatory divisions), east of 11°W, and west of 68°E. The FAO area codes included were 27.1.A, 27.1.B, 27.2.A.1, 27.2.A.2, 27.2.B.1, and 27.2.B.2. To isolate the demersal trawl fleet, the following ERS gear codes were selected: OT, OTB, OTT, PT, PTB, TB, TBB, and TX. In addition, a requirement was imposed that the dominant species in each catch (by weight) must be one of the main target whitefish species: cod, saithe, or

haddock. This criterion does not restrict the presence of other species in the catch, but ensures that the primary component belongs to one of these three target species.

To develop a fingerprinting system for Norwegian bottom trawling fisheries, we focused on extracting behavioural patterns from vessel tracking and catch data of the target fleet. This approach enabled us to summarise patterns in fishing and navigation activities, thereby facilitating the identification of anomalous activity that deviates from typical vessel behaviour. The target fleet comprises vessels conducting bottom trawling operations in the Barents Sea, primarily targeting whitefish species.

Detailed data sources are presented in Table 3. The temporal resolution for the VMS data was 10 minutes. Bottom trawling records in the ERS capture the start and end times and locations of each haul, along with gear specifications, target species, and estimated round weight. Consequently, fishing data inherently contains some degree of uncertainty and potential error.

Global anchorage data from Global Fishing Watch were merged with Norwegian port data to produce a comprehensive dataset of ports and anchorage sites, which was required for segmenting vessel activity into discrete fishing trips. Two environmental variables - sea depth (bathymetry) and seabed temperature - were incorporated to characterise trip behaviour. Bathymetric data were sourced from the General Bathymetric Grid of the Oceans (GEBCO), which provides a global, seamless terrain model integrating terrestrial topography with measured and modelled seafloor topography (Figure 3). Seabed temperature data were obtained from the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) global ocean physics reanalysis product.

Figure 3 GEBCO bathymetric data for the North Atlantic where the Norwegian bottom trawling fishery operates.

Table 3 Data Sources used to pre-process vessel tracking data and to extract feature information.

Data	Source
VMS	SINTEF Ocean: An SQLite Database collating data from Fiskeridirektoratet
ERS	Fiskeridirektoratet
Norwegian Port Location	Norwegian Coastal Administration (Kystverket)
Global Anchorage Site Location	Global Fishing Watch
Bathymetry	General bathymetric Grid of the Oceans (GEBCO) 2025
Sea Water Temperature at Sea Floor	Copernicus Marine Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis

3.2.2 Pre-processing and Fingerprinting

Data preprocessing comprised the following stages: integration of ERS and VMS data, merging of port information, trip segmentation, feature extraction, and generation of trip-level summaries. All geographic coordinate systems involving latitude and longitude utilise EPSG:4326 (WGS84), whilst projected coordinate systems for distance and buffer calculations employ EPSG:32632 (UTM Zone 32N, covering 6°E to 12°E in the northern hemisphere between the equator and 84°N). Duplicate records resulting from equipment failures were removed, such as instances where VMS data showed identical vessel call signs and timestamps but lacked location or heading information. The vessel call sign serves as the unique vessel identifier. This identifier was selected because licence names and permits may change with ownership transfers, whereas call signs remain relatively stable and distinctive.

Integration of VMS and ERS Data

The integration of ERS data with VMS trajectories was performed based on temporal windows for each vessel. This process involved matching VMS records to the start and end times of ERS hauling events, thereby associating fishing activities with corresponding tracked periods. Trajectory segments matched to ERS records were classified as "fishing", whilst unmatched VMS trajectories were designated as "not fishing". Prior to matching, as individual ERS records may document multiple target species within a single operation, species information and round weights were pivoted into single rows to prevent duplicate entries during the subsequent left join operation.

Consistent with the objective of retaining potentially anomalous data, unmatched ERS records were examined to identify and remove obviously erroneous entries, such as those originating from devices undergoing maintenance at inland locations (e.g., Slovenia). Among the remaining unmatched ERS events, some exhibited durations significantly shorter than the VMS reporting interval. To address this temporal mismatch, a search buffer of ± 1 hour was applied to the matching time window. Following this adjustment, certain ERS records remained unmatched because they occurred before the vessel's first VMS record of the year (e.g., a haul from 31 December 2022 23:50 to 1 January 2023 01:00, when the first 2023 VMS record was at 02:30). Such ERS entries were directly matched to the year's first VMS record. The remaining unmatched ERS records typically exhibited problematic characteristics, such as three hours of hauling activity within a 12-hour VMS data gap or records of substantial catches without corresponding tracking data. For these cases, we calculated the duration of the VMS data gap and determined the ratio of total trawling time within the gap to the gap's total duration.

Trip Segmentation

Following the integration of catch data with VMS trajectories, trip segmentation was conducted in accordance with the methodology described by Mendo et al. (2024). This approach identifies fishing trips by detecting vessel departures from, and arrivals to, ports or anchorage sites. Because Norwegian port data do not provide complete coverage, and vessels frequently anchor within the territorial waters of neighbouring countries, the Norwegian port dataset was merged with the Global Fishing Watch anchorage dataset. The consolidation was performed using 100-metre buffer zones around known port locations, with Norwegian port records taking precedence in cases of spatial overlap.

For each VMS position, depth and seabed temperature values were extracted by performing a three-dimensional spatial and temporal intersection with the relevant environmental datasets. Values were initially aggregated to calculate mean sea depth and seabed temperature for individual hauls, and subsequently aggregated again to produce trip-level means across all hauls within each trip.

To address variability in VMS reporting intervals, a 500-metre buffer was applied around all port locations to detect vessel entry and exit events. Once port-associated VMS points were identified, they were removed from vessel tracks while their timestamps were retained as markers of trip start and end. If a vessel's first or last VMS record of the year occurred at sea, this record was designated as the initial trip start or final trip end for that year. Trip identifiers were then assigned sequentially for each vessel (e.g., LERB_1). Basic trip-level metrics, such as duration (hours) and number of VMS records, were also computed. Invalid trips were

removed based on the following criteria: at least three VMS observations and a minimum travelled distance of 3 km.

Feature Engineering

When aggregating data at the trip level for anomaly detection modelling, the input features listed in Table 4 were aggregated and extracted from the pre-processed trip data.

Table 4 Trip-level features for anomaly detection.

Feature Name	Details
Trip Duration	Duration of trip (hours)
Total Fishing Hours	Total trawling duration (hours)
Number of Hauls	Total count of ERS events (i.e. trawling operations) in this trip
Fishing Time Proportion	Proportion of total trawling duration relative to trip duration
Trip Non-Fishing Sinuosity	Sinuosity of the trip trajectory during non-trawling periods, derived from time series and total non-trawling distance (m)
Trip Non-Fishing Straightness	Straightness of the trip trajectory during non-trawling periods, derived from time series and total non-trawling distance (m)
Trip Median Fishing Sinuosity	Median sinuosity of the trip trajectory during trawling operations, calculated from time series and individual trawling distances for all hauls in this trip (m)
Trip Median Fishing Straightness	Median straightness of the trip trajectory during trawling operations, calculated from time series and individual trawling distances for all hauls in this trip (m)
Mean Fishing Distance per Haul	Mean trawling distance per fishing operation in this trip (m)
Total Fishing Distance	Summed trawling distance for this trip (m)
Mean Fishing Depth	Mean trawling depth, extracted from bathymetry data (m)
Trip Mean Temperature	Mean seabed temperature during trawling operations (°C)
Sum Gap Ratio	Summed ratio of unmatched ERS time relative to VMS data gap duration
Gear Name*	Name of gears used in this trip: OTB, OTM, TBS, TM, PTM, TB, TMS, PS1, SSC, SV, SB
Gear Details	Deployment of gears used in this trip: Single Trawl, Double Trawl, Triple Trawl
Gear Minimum Mesh Size	Minimum gear mesh size used in this trip (mm)
Gear Maximum Mesh Size	Maximum gear mesh size used in this trip (mm)
Species Median CPUE**	Median catch per unit effort (CPUE) for each species across all hauls in this trip, obtained from reported round weight and hauling distance (Eqn. 2). Species included: GHL, POK, CMO, HKE, LIN, CAS, COD, HAD, REB, REG, CAA, HAL, PRA, USK, MZZ, POL, MAC, PLA, BLI, CAB, CAT, MON, DAB, ARU, WHB, ARG, WHG, SPR, RHG, HER, PLE, LEM, WIT, FLE, JCM, PLZ, PAN, SKA, RNG, LUM, CAP, POC, SRX

*: Gear names follow FAO International Standard Code. Full details and names are available from: [International Standard Statistical Classification of Fishing Gear - Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations](#).

** : Species names follow FAO ASFIS (Aquatic Sciences and Fisheries Information System) codes. Full details and names are available from: [ASFIS List of Species for Fishery Statistics Purposes - Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations](#).

Navigation and distance-related features (e.g., sinuosity, straightness) were calculated using Haversine distance (Equation 1) based on time series order. CPUE was calculated per haul according to Equation 2, which differs from traditional definitions by relating catch to hauling distance rather than time.

$$distance = 2R \arcsin\left(\sqrt{\sin^2 \frac{\Delta\varphi}{2} + \cos \varphi_1 \cos \varphi_2 \sin^2 \frac{\Delta\lambda}{2}}\right) \quad \text{Eqn. 1}$$

Where

R = Earth radius

$\Delta\varphi$ = difference in point latitudes

$\Delta\lambda$ = difference in point longitudes

$$CPUE = \frac{\text{Total catch in this hauling (round weight,kg)}}{\text{hauling distance (m)}} \quad \text{Eqn. 2}$$

3.2.3 Isolation Forest for Trip-Level Anomaly Detection

Algorithm Description and Rationale

Isolation Forest (iForest) is an unsupervised machine learning algorithm specifically designed for anomaly detection in high-dimensional datasets (Liu et al. 2008). Unlike density-based or distance-based methods, iForest operates on the principle that anomalies are "few and different", making them more susceptible to isolation than normal observations. The algorithm constructs an ensemble of isolation trees by recursively partitioning the feature space through random selection of features and split values. Anomalous instances require fewer random partitions to be isolated compared to normal instances, resulting in shorter path lengths from the root to terminal nodes.

We selected iForest for this analysis for several reasons. First, the algorithm demonstrates computational efficiency with linear time complexity and low memory requirements, making it suitable for large-scale fisheries datasets containing thousands of trips. Second, iForest requires no assumptions about data distribution and performs robustly in high-dimensional feature spaces without the need for extensive parameter tuning. Third, the algorithm excels at detecting anomalies that deviate across multiple dimensions simultaneously, which is particularly relevant for fishing trip behaviour where anomalous patterns may manifest through complex combinations of navigational, temporal, and catch-related features. Finally, iForest provides anomaly scores that quantify the degree of abnormality for each observation, enabling flexible threshold selection and prioritisation of suspicious trips for further investigation.

Model Implementation and Interpretation

Before model training, feature engineering was performed at the vessel level. Redundant features representing species with no recorded catches were removed, and trips without any hauling records were excluded from the analysis, as the focus was specifically on trips with documented fishing activities. The iForest model was trained using a contamination rate (expected proportion of anomalies) of 1%, reflecting the assumption that most fishing trips exhibit normal behaviour whilst a small fraction may involve suspicious activities. This contamination parameter directly influences the decision threshold for classifying observations and in practice results in only one trip per vessel being classified as anomalous. Trips were assigned binary labels: 1 for normal behaviour and -1 for anomalous behaviour. The model generates an anomaly score for each trip, which is inversely related to the average path length required to isolate the observation across all trees in the ensemble.

To facilitate interpretation of the results for anomalous trips, z-scores were calculated for each feature used in the iForest algorithm to classify a trip. The z-score (unit: standard deviations) indicates the magnitude and direction of deviation from normal behaviour patterns for a given feature measured on a given trip. The z-scores were calculated as follows, where the mean of that feature for trips classified as normal is subtracted from the mean of the feature from an anomalous trip, and the difference is divided by the standard deviation of the feature for normal trips:

$$z - score = \frac{Mean(anomaly) - Mean(normal)}{Standard\ deviation(normal\ group)}$$

Positive z-scores indicate values above the mean of the distribution of that feature for trips classified as normal, whilst negative z-scores indicate values below the mean. These standardised scores enable comparison of feature contributions across different measurement scales.

We also calculated a consistency score,

$$consistency = 2 |p - 0.5|,$$

where p is the proportion of cases where the z-score is greater than zero, indicating a positive deviation from the mean. This calculation rescales deviation asymmetry to the interval [0,1] and can be used as a measure of consistency in the direction of deviation, where a value of 1 indicated that all z-scores had the same sign, while 0 means that there was an equal proportion of positive and negative z-scores.

4. Results

4.1. Danish gillnet fisheries

4.1.1. Predicting fishing operations

Four of the EM vessels had enough AIS/VMS points to test and validate the RF model on this type of data. The prediction results for these 4 vessels with good coverage are shown in Table 4. For one of the vessels, 94% of the trips reached an accuracy higher than 90 percent (i.e. predicted points matching the ground truth). In contrast when using the classical speed filter approach where hauling is deemed to be points of speed between 0 and 4 knots, the accuracy pr vessels varied between 52% and 76%.

Table 5 Accuracy of the model RF model and speed filter predictions on EM and AIS/VSM data.

Encrypted vessel ID	Speed filter accuracy on EM data	RF Prediction accuracy on EM data	Speed filter accuracy on AIS/VMS data	RF Prediction accuracy on AIS/VMS data
EXIUgY	66	93	52	89
FrYxWg	78	97	76	95
ldXTcf	66	96	64	87
xaoePt	71	95	71	89

In trips where the model did not perform well at predicting hauling, this was typically due to poor quality of the positional data, as shown in Figure 4. Here, it was clear that larger gaps between points in the trip can lead to underestimation of hauling points, especially if this occurs in the middle part of a trip. In single trips with relatively high false positive rates, it appeared that some of the complex sailing patterns with a lot of turns and sudden changes in speed tended to reduce model accuracy (Figure 5). Lastly, we noted that there were no cases of the model confusing setting events with hauling events.

Figure 4 An example of position data with big gaps between points, where the model underestimates hauling.

Figure 5 An example of how more complex sailing pattern can lead to a higher rate of false positives.

For the 4 selected vessels, 5743 hauling events with associated validated soak times were recorded using EM. Only 2306 hauling events were detected in the AIS/VMS dataset which matched specific hauling events identified in the EM dataset. The performance in detecting hauling events using AIS/VMS data varied per vessel and ranged from 21– 61% of all hauling events (Table 5).

Table 6 Numbers of hauls per vessel using EM data and AIS/VMS data

Encrypted vessel ID	Number of hauls EM	Number of hauling events inferred AIS/VMS	Percentage of hauling events inferred AIS/VMS
EXIUgY	1245	768	62
FrYxWg	1986	434	22
ldXTcf	1634	769	47
xaoePt	878	335	38

To explore the application of this approach at the fleet level, we applied the RF model to estimate the sum of lengths of nets set (or hauled) during one year of gillnet fishing (Figure 6). Here, prediction was possible for 121 vessels out of 719. Still, the selected vessels account for 74.8 % of the total landings (in weight) in the selected year.

Figure 6 Random forest predicted net length for one years of data aggregated to 0.01 degrees square

4.1.2. Soak time predictions

Soak times were estimated for 1230 hauling events identified from AIS/VMS data. The remaining hauling events could not be linked to a preceding setting event. For hauling events detected using AIS, predicted soak times aligned reasonably well with observed values (Fig. 7; overall $R^2 = 0.72$). In general, AIS-derived soak time estimates tended to be higher than the observed times, although the degree of overestimation varied among vessels (Figure 8). Anomalous soak times were present in vessel IdXTcf and xaoePt (Figure 9).

Figure 7 Relationship between EM-derived soak time and inferred soak time from AIS/VMS data. The dashed line represents a 1:1 relationship between observed and predicted soak times.

Figure 8 Histograms showing the distribution of differences (hours) between estimated soak time and EM derived soak time

Figure 9 Potential soak time anomalies (soak time outliers) in each vessel.

4.2. Norwegian bottom trawling fisheries

4.2.1 Overview of Results and Aggregated Feature Analysis

In 2023, the bottom-trawling fleet consisted of 41 vessels. However, the anomaly detection procedure produced results for only 40 vessels. Vessel JXNX was excluded from further analysis because it recorded only six trips during the year, of which only two contained ERS data. All trips for this vessel occurred in December, and the limited sample size was deemed insufficient for meaningful comparison or reliable anomaly detection.

Table 6 presents the full set of trips identified as anomalous in 2023, comprising a total of 40 flagged instances across the fleet. To examine the characteristics that differentiate anomalous trips from typical fleet behaviour, z-score values from all flagged trips were aggregated and analysed across multiple feature dimensions. Features with a score of zero were excluded, as these correspond to species not caught or gear types not used on a given trip and therefore do not contribute discriminative information.

Table 7 Anomalous trips in 2023

3YHX_11	3YYB_26	JXJU_16	LCLP_9	LJBC_163	LJPH_49	LJWI_14	LLAJ_22
LCMP_23	LDAL_12	LDAR_23	LDBR_31	LLAY_36	LLDH_15	LLIA_37	LLMI_85
LDBT_16	LDCO_26	LDDF_17	LDDG_26	LLOP_21	LMAC_23	LMBG_41	LNKS_29
LDNV_34	LDSF_3	LEBB_27	LEGQ_26	LFNX_24	LFOC_34	LFPE_10	LFRA_23
LERB_92	LFBW_15	LFGW_45	LFNT_13	LFVX_20	LGJY_26	LHMF_47	LHXV_32

Recurring features at the trip level

Analysis of the five most deviated features from each anomalous trip reveals some recurring patterns. Table 7 shows the frequency of feature recurrence among the top five absolute z-scores across all anomalous trips. Gear mesh size parameters are the most frequently observed anomalous features, with maximum mesh size observed in 12 trips (mean absolute z-score of 5.68) and minimum mesh size in 10 trips (mean absolute z-score of 4.37). These features exhibit deviations in varying directions, indicating that anomalous mesh sizes occur both above and below typical values. Mean hauling depth also features prominently, occurring in 12 anomalous trips with a mean absolute z-score of 2.27, whilst the use of single trawl configurations appears in 9 trips with a mean absolute z-score of 4.34. The catch species that occurred most frequently in the top five largest absolute z-scores was beaked redfish, with a large mean absolute z-score of 6.05.

Table 8 The frequency of occurrence of the top five features with largest deviations from normal trips based on z-scores.

Feature	Count (out of 40)	Mean absolute z-score	Direction of Deviation
Gear mesh size max	12	5.68	Varying
Mean hauling depth	12	2.27	Varying
Gear mesh size min	10	4.37	Varying
Single Trawl	9	4.34	Varying
Sinuosity when not trawling	8	9.38	Varying
Species REB (Beaked redfish)	7	6.05	Varying
Double Trawl	7	3.70	Varying
Total fishing hours	7	1.64	Consistently higher than mean
Species CAA (Atlantic wolffish)	7	1.57	Varying
Species HAL (Atlantic halibut)	7	1.46	Varying
Species PRA (Northern prawn)	6	5.09	Varying
Trip duration hours	6	1.57	Consistently higher than mean
Species COD (Atlantic cod)	6	1.3	Consistently lower than mean

Notably, sinuosity when not trawling has the highest mean absolute z-score (9.38) among frequently occurring features, appearing in eight anomalous trips. This suggests that unusual navigational patterns during non-fishing periods constitute a powerful indicator of anomalous behaviour. Several species-specific features also emerge as essential discriminators, including beaked redfish (REB, 7 occurrences), Atlantic wolffish (CAA, 7 occurrences), Atlantic halibut (HAL, 7 occurrences), and northern prawn (PRA, 6 occurrences). The direction of deviation varies across features, with some showing consistent patterns such as total fishing hours and trip duration being consistently higher than mean values, whilst others exhibit departures in both directions.

Features with extreme deviations at the fleet level

Analysis of extreme feature values (Table 8) identifies features that frequently exhibit z-scores exceeding 3 standard deviations from the mean across trips from all vessels, representing statistically significant departures from normal behaviour ($p < 0.01$). Gear mesh size was a recurrent feature in anomalous trips that was consistently different to what would be expected for normal trips. In other words, gear mesh size is usually stable and when changes occur this contributes strongly to the detection of an anomalous trip. Other features with frequent extreme values include mean hauling depth (8 occurrences), sinuosity when not

trawling (7 occurrences), and catches of specific species such as beaked redfish and Atlantic wolffish (7 occurrences each).

Table 9 Frequency of occurrence of 11 features with extreme z-score (counts when absolute z-score > 3).

Feature	Frequency	Mean absolute z-score	Direction of Deviation
Gear mesh size max	13	5.68	Varying
Gear mesh size min	11	4.37	Varying
Mean hauling depth	8	2.27	Varying
Sinuosity when not trawling	7	9.38	Varying
Species REB (Beaked redfish)	7	6.05	Varying
Species CAA (Atlantic wolffish)	7	1.57	Varying
Species COD (Atlantic cod)	7	1.30	Consistently lower than mean
Species PRA (Northern prawn)	6	5.09	Varying
Single Trawl	6	4.34	Varying
Double Trawl	6	3.70	Varying
Trip duration hours	6	1.57	Consistently higher than mean

Directional Consistency of Deviations

Examination of directional consistency (Table 9) shows that certain features deviate consistently in specific directions when they contribute to anomaly scores, providing insight into the nature of anomalous behaviour. Species RNG and RHG exhibit perfect directional consistency (100% positive z-scores), indicating that when these species appear in anomalous catches, they are invariably present in quantities exceeding typical levels. This pattern suggests potential unreported bycatch or targeting of non-traditional species. Conversely, several features demonstrate consistent negative deviations. European hake (HKE, 14.3% positive z-scores), mean hauling temperature (15% positive), and tusk (USK, 21.9% positive) all show strong tendencies towards values below normal ranges in anomalous trips. Notably, Atlantic cod catches show consistent negative deviation (22.5% positive z-scores), which may indicate underreporting of this commercially valuable species or shifts to alternative target species during certain operations. These patterns may reflect fishing activities in atypical environmental conditions or areas, potentially indicating unreported fishing grounds or seasonal variations in behaviour. Features such as trip duration (77.5% positive z-scores), total hauling distance (77.5% positive), and total fishing hours (75% positive) demonstrate moderate consistency towards higher values, suggesting that anomalous trips often involve extended operations or greater spatial coverage.

Table 10 Features with the highest consistency in direction of deviation from normal trips. The condition of inclusion is that the feature appears at least three times in the top five features.

Feature	Percentage of Positive z-scores	Consistency	Direction
Species RNG (Roundnose grenadier)	100.0	1	Consistently higher than mean
Species RHG (Roughhead grenadier)	100.0	1	Consistently higher than mean
Species HKE (hake)	14.3	0.714	Consistently lower than mean
Mean hauling temperature	15.0	0.7	Consistently lower than mean
Species USK (Tusk)	21.9	0.562	Consistently lower than mean
Trip duration hours	77.5	0.55	Consistently higher than mean
Species COD	22.5	0.55	Consistently lower than mean
Total hauling distance	77.5	0.55	Consistently higher than mean
Total fishing hours	75.0	0.5	Consistently higher than mean
Species POK (pollock)	25.0	0.5	Consistently lower than mean

4.2.3 Examples of anomalous trips

The iForest model demonstrates robust performance in capturing anomalies across various behavioural dimensions. Examination of specific anomalous trips from individual vessels reveals diverse patterns of suspicious activity (Figure 10).

Figure 10 Examples of anomalous trips for vessels a) LEBB, b) LFRA, c) LDAL, and d) LFNT. Normal trajectories are shown in grey in each case

The model successfully identified trips involving hauling operations at exceptionally distant locations, as illustrated for vessels LEBB and LFRA in Figure 10, as well as significant detours to remote fishing grounds or ports. Notably, the model exhibits appropriate discrimination, correctly classifying specific trips to distant fishing grounds as normal behaviour, demonstrating its capacity to distinguish between legitimate operational variations and genuinely anomalous activity. Several anomalous trips were detected that involved trawling in proximity to port locations. The model also captured trips exhibiting unusual transit patterns, including trajectories that traversed multiple ports in approximately straight lines over extended periods or demonstrated unusually prolonged dwelling times at specific locations (Figure 11).

Interestingly, some anomalous trips display trajectories that appear relatively normal and indistinguishable from routine trips to regular fishing grounds (Figure 10: vessels LDAL, LFNT). However, a detailed examination using z-score analysis reveals that the primary anomalies in these trips lie in catch composition and CPUE values for specific species, rather than in navigational patterns. For vessel LFNT, the principal anomalous characteristics comprise exceptionally high sinuosity during non-trawling periods, substantial yields of beaked redfish (REB), and the deployment of specific gear configurations (PTM, single trawl). Notably, the latter two characteristics precisely correspond to the top three most anomalous features observed for vessel LDAL. This pattern may reflect the abundance of beaked redfish in particular fishing areas and the requirement for specialised gear configurations during their capture, suggesting that whilst these trips involve legitimate fishing operations, they deviate significantly from typical fleet behaviour patterns and warrant further investigation to verify compliance with regulations and catch reporting accuracy.

Figure 11. Two examples of anomalous trips and associated z-scores.

5. Discussion and conclusions

5.1. Danish gillnet fisheries

The present case study evaluated the feasibility of using AIS and VMS data to estimate soak time in the Danish gillnet fishery, using highly resolved EM data for training and validation. First, a method to infer fishing activities was developed using a random forest (RF) model, which potentially could improve the accuracy of inferred fishing in the Danish gillnet fleet from 64% to 85%. Seeing as the model far outperforms the speed filter method, it is currently being implemented in the Danish national workflow for improving the identification of gillnet fishing effort.

The second main objective of this case study was to assess whether soak time could be reliably estimated from AIS/VMS data, with a view to supporting fleet-wide implementation. However, this approach still faces challenges related to data quality, as AIS records often contain gaps that hinder accurate soak-time estimation, while VMS ping rates are too long to perform well with the RF model we developed. Of the 10 vessels equipped with EM and initially considered, only four had sufficiently complete AIS/VMS data to be included in the analysis. Fewer than half of the EM-reported hauls were detected in the AIS/VMS dataset. Nevertheless, for the hauls that were successfully matched, the models showed encouraging performance in predicting soak time ($R^2 = 0.72$). These encouraging results, together with previous positive findings using EM data (Mendo et al., 2023), suggest that—with an appropriate sampling frequency—soak times and associated anomalies could be reliably estimated in gillnet fisheries using geospatial data alone.

When looking to evaluate the gillnet effort on fleet level it is apparent that the quality of positions data is the deciding factor. For predicting hauling, the positions data just needs to be good for the individual trips to give decent results as shown on the attempt to map out the fleet net lengths for one year. For inferring the soaking time, it is important that the vessel has consistent coverage without gaps, otherwise the result of the prediction quickly becomes unreliable. With AIS being a safety feature that can be turned off at will, it is therefore not ideal for predicting soaking time of passive gear fisheries.

5.2. Norwegian bottom trawling fisheries

The second case study evaluated the feasibility of “fingerprinting” vessels by considering a range of features including movement, catch and environmental conditions to facilitate anomaly detection at scales relevant for control. Anomalies in fisheries often only consider positional data, here we developed a method to flag potentially irregular fishing behaviour that can also offer interpretable explanations. We show examples of its successful application to a dataset from the Norwegian bottom trawling fishery for detecting anomalies in fishing activities at the trip-level.

Future work could incorporate quota information and application of the methodology presented here at the fleet level, to fingerprint the behaviour of the fleet and detect vessels with anomalous behaviours. A methodological extension could be to explore the use of a more stochastic analytical approach, such as hidden Markov models, for identifying anomalous trips. A major advantage of a stochastic approach is that the number of anomalous trips would not be user-defined as it is in iForest where the contamination threshold needs to be chosen a priori.

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